

SUSBOARD Project to Deliver 100% Bio-based Adhesives for Wood Boards

Vienna, 30 September 2025 – A new Horizon Europe project, [SUSBOARD](#), has launched to transform the wood panel and furniture industries. It will develop 100% biobased, formaldehyde-free and cost-competitive adhesive for particleboard (PB) and medium-density fibreboard (MDF).

Every year, Europe produces around **60 million m³ of PB and MDF**, both of which are essential materials for construction and furniture manufacturing. Today, these boards still rely on fossil-based adhesives that emit formaldehyde and contribute significantly to carbon emissions. With a budget of €9,1 million, SUSBOARD will deliver an innovative alternative that not only meets industry performance standards but also supports **Europe's path to climate neutrality**.

“SUSBOARD is a strong example of how science and industry can work hand in hand to deliver tangible solutions for Europe's Green Deal Industrial Plan,” said **RTDS Association**, project coordinator.

Building on the success of the [SUSBIND](#) project, which achieved more than 80% renewable raw materials in adhesives, SUSBOARD will **complete the transition** by introducing a fully bio-based amine component. This breakthrough is expected to **reduce the carbon footprint of wood boards by up to 30%** while eliminating formaldehyde-related health risks for consumers and workers.

“SUSBOARD is bringing new possibilities to the wood panel and furniture industries. Our project will demonstrate that 100% bio-based adhesives can deliver competitive performance and cost efficiency while supporting Europe's climate objectives,” added **Wood K plus**, the project's scientific coordinator.

The project aligns closely with the **European Green Deal, Circular Economy Action Plan, and Zero Pollution Action Plan**, supporting Europe's shift towards a fossil-free and greener future. By cutting industrial carbon emissions, reducing volatile organic compound (VOC) emissions, and fully eliminating formaldehyde-related health risks, SUSBOARD will contribute to healthier indoor environments and safer working conditions.

Over the next four years, the project will:

- Scale production of the new adhesive to **multi-ton levels**;
- Demonstrate performance on **industrial production lines**;
- Test applications in **furniture manufacturing**;
- Develop a **prototype modular furniture product**;
- Ensure sustainability through a full **Safe and Sustainable by Design** assessment.

The project unites leading research institutes, global chemical companies, and major wood panel producers from Austria, Germany, Portugal, and Turkey, including: **RTDS Association, Wood K plus, IHD Dresden, Cargill, BASF SE, Sonae Arauco, Kastamonu Entegre, Balorman INT, and Saréco**.

The official **kick-off meeting** was held in Tulln, Austria, from **24–26 June 2025**, hosted by Wood K plus.

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SUSBOARD will share updates through its **new website, newsletter, and social media channels**. Follow the project on [LinkedIn](#), [X](#), and [Zenodo](#) for the latest news and results.